

Mobility analytics and COVID-19 in Greece

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Abstract. This work is focused on multi-aspect analytics of epidemic data, using Greece as the use case for assessing the national outbreak and estimating the general trends and outlook of it since the beginning of the pandemic in early 2020 up to the end of 2020. Using methodologies from compartmentalized epidemic modelling, data analytics and machine learning, several insights are presented with regard to early tracking of the evolving outbreak, despite having to deal with data scarcity, inconsistencies and quality issues. It is intended to be used as a guideline for data-related challenges on producing actionable information to decision-makers during an active epidemic.

Keywords: COVID-19 · SARS-CoV-2 · Greece · data analytics · SEIR · predictive modelling · data restoration · computational epidemics · epidemic tracking.

1 Introduction

In the beginning of 2020 the world landed into a pandemic of intensity and scale that has not been manifested for many decades. A global spread of flu-like infectious disease started spreading fast across countries via international travel and, although the first signs of it appeared as early as November 2019 in Wuhan, China [11], it took at least two or three more months before the rest of the world realized the seriousness of the situation. By then, it was already too late and the SARS-CoV-2 virus had reached most of the countries world-wide, at least those with international flights.

One of the most apparent drawbacks and deficiencies of the current monitoring of epidemic diseases by authorities like ECDC (EU), CDC (USA) and WHO is in the availability of timely, accurate and information-rich epidemic data. The COVID-19 pandemic is the first such event in the era of big data, rapid dissemination and knowledge sharing at the global scale. Yet, this outbreak revealed that data availability is not guaranteed in such situations. The reporting of infected cases presents significant challenges for several reasons, including data inconsistencies, delays, saturation of health infrastructure, etc.

A full century after the Spanish flu pandemic (1918-1920) that infected 500 million people, a third of the world's population at the time, and resulted in 50 million fatalities, the COVID-19 pandemic exhibits four major differences:

- International travelling, especially via flights, is perhaps the most crucial multiplier in the spreading of the disease. Before the virus was even isolated for study, it reached every major international airport on the planet, infecting many thousands of unaware travellers.
- Modern societies are organized mostly in urban grids and mega-cities, resulting in high-density populations in relatively localized areas. This is the second most significant factor regarding the spreading of highly infectious diseases and an important societal change from what was the situation a century ago.
- Scientific knowledge and medical resources are now vastly superior to what was available a century ago, at least for most countries.
- Current technology enables the gathering, processing and analysis of huge amounts of data at a planetary scale. Within hours at most, every new evidence, laboratory result and scientific breakthrough about the new virus was disseminated via the Internet, mostly in open-access papers and data repositories.

While the first three items characterize modern societies and dictate the current requirements and constraints when dealing with such pandemics, the fourth item constitutes one of the most important mitigation factors and scientific tools to achieve such a goal. Although each epidemic or pandemic is different from the others, there is now a significant body of knowledge with regard to the data-aware and data-driven epidemic monitoring of it, ranging from country-wide statistics and trends to high-resolution regional risk assessments and tracking of human mobility. These novel capabilities constitute not only a predictive tool for evaluating the status of the crisis, but also the inherent characteristics of the pathogen and how it spreads. This second function became more evident in this current pandemic, with thousands of research teams processing world-wide epidemic data, running computational experiments and estimating the true nature of the SARS-CoV-2 virus before even the first genome studies were available.

In this chapter, the data-driven analysis of the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic is addressed via various approaches of gradual complexity and refinement. In particular, using Greece as the main use case, the epidemic is analysed at the national level under the scope of different viewpoints:

1. Compartmentalized SEIR-like modelling: This is the standard, well-established way of tracking the evolution of an infectious disease using a well-defined dynamic system of equations and employing several assumptions about how it behaves in distinct states or 'compartments'.
2. Machine learning modelling: Having realistic predictive analytics for the epidemic requires the lifting of ad-hoc assumptions and simplifications of the underlying dynamics that describe the real-world process. Machine learning enables the design and implementation of purely data-driven models that approximate this process with high accuracy and predictive value.

3. Human mobility analytics: Since the spread of flu-like highly infectious diseases depends mostly on human activities, social interactions and population density, mobility tracking in residential areas, workplaces, travel hubs, etc, is inherently a crucial indicator and in some cases even a predictor in relation to epidemics.

Greece is a perfect example for describing the three approaches, each of which has specific advantages and difficulties in actual implementation. More data usually mean more options towards human mobility analytics and Machine Learning modelling, but on the other hand this is not easy to obtain in the early phases of an outbreak. Similarly, human mobility data and urban flows, e.g., transportation of passengers in buses and metro stations, are now more readily available than accurate epidemic data at a regional level, but only indicative (indirect) of what is happening or is about to happen regarding the evolution of the outbreak.

The rest of the chapter is organized as follows: Section 2 describes the challenges and drawbacks related to the availability of epidemic data; section 3 summarizes the standard compartmentalized epidemic models and presents its application to Greece; section 4 provides a quick overview of approaches from signal processing, adaptive filtering and Machine Learning in general; section 5 describes the aspect of human mobility data in the scope of the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic; subsequently, section 6 describes how these data can be used in association with epidemic modelling and analytics; finally, section 7 summarizes the conclusions and lessons learned.

2 Coping with degraded data quality and availability

History has shown that the close tracking of an epidemic outbreak, especially at its early stages, is hard. Regardless if it is a small-scale event of a new variant of a known virus or a global-scale pandemic that spreads across countries within weeks, there is significant time between the onset of the disease, the first confirmed detections, the proper epidemic monitoring and, finally, the systematic logging of detailed, reliable data from the healthcare workflow.

There are inherent difficulties in early detection of new strains or completely novel viruses, mostly due to the lack of readily available reliable methods of tracking a highly infectious disease in the general population (time is needed before the genome of the virus is analysed, delayed reporting of confirmed infections, deaths and recoveries, undetected cases of infected people, etc). A highly contagious disease like the Spanish flu may be affecting a huge portion of the general population but remain largely undetected if the symptoms and escalation are very mild, while more subtle outbreaks like with the ebola virus are clearly evident due to its lethality, yet much ‘slower’ with regard to spreading rates.

In data analytics for epidemic modelling, these factors are manifested in the form of data quality degradations of various types, ranging from partial time

inconsistencies and noise factors to large portions of missing data or even complete lack of some categories of them [20]. In these cases, the modelling approach has to be adapted, reconfigured and designed specifically to cope with such deficiencies, employing both data restoration and proper selection of modelling methods, capable of providing the inputs and tools required to reach the goals that are usually two-fold: (a) provide insights about the outbreak and, indirectly, the inherent properties of the virus; and (b) provide some level or short- or long-term prediction regarding the evolution of the outbreak, in order to improve the decision-making process and mitigation planning.

The following sections provide such insights for epidemic data deficiencies, modelling and restoration methods, using the SARS-CoV-2 epidemic in Greece as the use case. Early stages of the outbreak, i.e., end of February to end of April 2020, are examined in terms of modelling the exponential growth of infections, deaths and recoveries, and these quantities are revisited a few weeks later, when data deficiencies start becoming even more evident. Restoration methods and subsequent actions can be considered as the necessary data pre-processing stages before the analytical methods for epidemic modelling, which are presented in subsequent sections further on.

2.1 Infections, Deaths, Recoveries

Using the $I(t)$ data series the following exponential formulation can be designed according to Eq.1 [11]:

$$I(t) \approx e^{a-be^{-ct}} \quad (1)$$

where a, b, c are the function parameters. Their best-fit optimal values in the least-squares (LSE) sense [28] and the 95% confidence intervals for Greece are presented in Table 1. The first set of parameters (second column) refers to the best-fit values with data up to April 14th [11], while the second set (third column) refers to the updated best-fit values including all data up to May 3rd. It is clear that the composite exponential growth model is valid throughout this period with minimal updates to the best-fit parameters.

Table 1. LSE-optimal function parameters in Eq.1 for Greece. Upper half refers to data up to April 14th, lower half refers to data up to May 3rd.

Parameter	Apr. 14th	May 3rd
a	8.097 (7.974, 8.221)	7.986 (7.941, 8.030)
b	8.722 (8.420, 9.024)	8.787 (8.517, 9.058)
c	0.064 (0.060, 0.068)	0.068 (0.065, 0.070)

Figure 1 presents the difference between a ‘naive’ exponential $y(t) = e^{cx(t)}$ (red) with only one parameter and the good fit ($R^2=0.992$, RMSE=0.017) of Eq.1 (magenta). In the second case it is clear that the function design, i.e., an exponentially saturating formula, as well as a linear error weighting that

is applied towards the more recent date range, provides the very robust set of optimized parameters that Table 1 presents. It should also be noted that, as the $I(t)$ becomes more linear due to the gradual slow-down of the national outbreak, the exponential factor c in Eq.1 and Table 1 converges to zero and factors a and b increase, i.e., the value of $I(t)$ asymptotically approaches its upper threshold as it crossed well inside phase 5a of the epidemic and moves towards its ‘peak’.

Fig. 1. ‘Naive’ exponential $y(t) = e^{cx(t)}$ (red) with only one parameter and the good fit of Eq.1 (magenta) for Greece. ($R^2=0.992$, $RMSE=0.017$)

One thing that is clearly evident from the publicly available epidemic data for Greece, especially for the period after mid-April, is the severe delay in reporting the recovered $R(t)$ daily values. This constitutes a major issue in terms of data quality and, in turn, create significant difficulties in producing accurate and well-fitted epidemic models like SEIQRDP which depend heavily on $I(t)$, $D(t)$ and $R(t)$. This is a common observation in large-scale epidemics especially during in the period close to the peak of infections, mostly due to the rapidly evolving situation and the inherent delays in registering these numbers in official data reports.

In order to cope with such quality degradation of the epidemic data, an additional pre-processing step was implemented in this work for $R(t)$ reconstruction. More specifically, the overall fatality rate against confirmed cases is estimated well within the global values from other countries with similar incident intensity (cases per 100,000 of population) and COVID-19 testing policies [11]. Therefore, since all Deaths $D(t)$ are confirmed and logged with proper procedures in hospitals, these can be reasonably considered a reliable baseline for both $I(t)$ and $R(t)$ assessment in terms of data quality, under-reporting rates and subsequent missing values. It should be noted that active infections are calculated as $a.I(t) = I(t) - \hat{R}(t)$, i.e., a reliable estimation of $R(t)$ is still required even if $I(t)$ (cumulative) is accurate. In practice, every single-day official reporting of $R(t)$ is used as a reference point and high-quality interpolation against t , specifically

a spline-like piecewise cubic Hermite interpolating polynomial (‘pchip’) [10, 13], is employed for estimating the intermediate missing values for $R(t)$. Additional interpolation options were assessed for the same process, including $D(t)$ instead of t as the series baseline, i.e., estimate via daily deaths which is a relatively reliable data series. The ‘pchip’ interpolation was also compared and confirmed as superior from quadratic spline, in terms of variability from the reference baseline of piecewise linear. Figure 2 presents the interpolation process of $\hat{R}(t)$ directly against time (t), illustrating the reference points (circles) interpolated with linear (blue), quadratic spline (magenta) and ‘pchip’ (red) functions; the third is chosen in this work as the best interpolator for its shape-preserving properties [25].

Fig. 2. Interpolation $\hat{R}(t)$ of Recovered $R(t)$ against time (t).

2.2 Under-reporting of Infections ($I(t)$)

One of the most discussed issues regarding the outbreak in Greece is the under-reporting of infections $I(t)$ and how this affects the epidemic models, as well as the confidence in planning the mitigation policies. It has to be recognized, assessed in terms of magnitude and addressed via proper pre-processing within the predictive models. One such pre-processing step is the restoration of $\hat{R}(t)$ as described previously.

It has been accepted by state officials that the under-reporting of $I(t)$ in Greece may be up to 20:1 (only 1 in 20 infections registered) or more, given the numbers from other countries and the targeted-only tests in Greece. In the update on April 14th [11], separate SEIQRDP models were evaluated with different assumptions regarding the extent of the under-reporting of $I(t)$. According to

those models, the projected dates of peak infections ranged from April 15th to May 5th, associated to no under-reporting ($f_{low}^I = 1.0$) up to a ratio of almost 1:10 ($f_{high}^I = 9.5$) for under-reporting, respectively. The availability of more recent epidemic data up to May 3rd well beyond the actual peak of $I(t)$ as described previously enable the revisiting of those projections and, hence, the validity of the associated under-reporting assumptions. More specifically, the actual peak date of 20-21 of April falls between the cases April 16th ($f^I = 1.08$) or April 25th ($f^I = 4.5$). By a rough linear regression (LR) estimation, this translates to $2.60 \leq f^I \leq 2.98$, i.e., indicating under-reporting level for $I(t)$ no more than 1:3. Additional hints regarding the under-reporting can be investigated via the Deaths $D(t)$ and ICU used compared to the infections $I(t)$ and active infections $a.I(t)$, respectively.

3 Standard epidemic modelling: SIR/SEIR

The mathematical modelling of epidemics has been a very active research field for decades, even before sources with detailed data were available. By far, the most popular and well-established approach is the family of *compartmental epidemic models*, originally developed as far back as 1920s. Their common characteristic is the base assumption of having a target population partitioned in *compartments* that are homogeneous in all relevant properties (e.g., sex, age, underlying pathologies, etc) and there are direct interactions between them. The three basic compartments are S='susceptible', I='infectious' and R='recovered', assuming insignificant rate of deaths and permanent immunity after recovery. Variants of this SIR base model include a D='deaths' compartment (SIRD), E='exposed' compartment (SEIR, SEIRD) for introducing an incubation period, Q='quarantined' compartment (SEIQRD, SEIQRDP) for separating the already isolated confirmed/possible carriers, etc. The SIR-like models, along with more recent SEIR-like variants, are still used as the baseline for comparing other approaches to epidemic modelling. These are usually based on Sequential Monte Carlo [24, 31], Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) or Markov Chain quasi-Monte Carlo (MCQMC) [29, 7, 17], Hidden Markov Models (HMM) [27, 4, 3, 30], etc, each posing other assumptions, advantages and drawbacks - most commonly the availability or not of a significant amount of epidemic data upon which they are to be trained.

The SEIR-like epidemic modelling is closely related to the Lotka–Volterra system of equations [18], developed in the 1910s to describe the evolution of dynamic systems via differential equations. They constitute an example of the more generic Kolmogorov model [9, 6] which can describe the dynamics of ecological systems with predator–prey interactions, competition, disease, etc.

Based on recent models that are already being tested with COVID-19 data from China and other countries, the current work explored the (still scarce) epidemic data for Greece via the generic framework of a SEIQRDP model setup [22, 21]. The additional P='insusceptible' corresponds to a fraction of the general population (if any) that, even when exposed to the virus, cannot become

Fig. 3. The block diagram of the SEIQRDP model and its parameters.

‘infected’ and, thus, does not enter the E compartments and stays outside the ‘pipeline’ of the epidemic. Each interaction between the SEIQRDP compartments is governed by a scalar parameter that governs the way fractions of each subset is ‘transferred’ to another, e.g., from ‘infected’ to ‘recovered’. Figure 3 illustrates the SEIQRDP model and the meaning of each parameter. The internal structure of the model, i.e., the interactions that describe the dynamics of the system, is formulated by Eq.2 through Eq.8.

$$\frac{dS(t)}{dt} = -\beta \frac{S(t)I(t)}{N} - \alpha S(t) \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{dE(t)}{dt} = \beta \frac{S(t)I(t)}{N} - \gamma E(t) \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{dI(t)}{dt} = \gamma E(t) - \delta I(t) \quad (4)$$

$$\frac{dQ(t)}{dt} = \delta I(t) - \lambda(t)Q(t) - \kappa(t)Q(t) \quad (5)$$

$$\frac{dR(t)}{dt} = \lambda(t)Q(t) \quad (6)$$

$$\frac{dD(t)}{dt} = \kappa(t)Q(t) \quad (7)$$

$$\frac{dP(t)}{dt} = \alpha S(t) \quad (8)$$

Each of the parameters of SEIQRDP model in the block diagram of Figure 3 and the corresponding system of differential equations provide very important hints regarding the dynamics of the underlying system, i.e., the evolution of the epidemic that the model describes, given enough data are available as ground truth.

Based on the compartmentalized SIR/SEIR approach, a SEIQRDP model was designed and trained using the $I(t)$, $D(t)$ and $R(t)$ data series for Greece, from end of February to early May 2020. The purpose of this work was to

re-estimate the general properties of SARS-CoV-2 virus and the COVID-19 outbreak on the national level, in order to: (a) confirm that the available data series are adequate and their evolution is in accordance to the research outcomes from other countries and on world-wide level; and (b) estimate the progress of the outbreak on the mid-/long-term level, specifically for the epidemic phases, the expected peak date and magnitude, etc.

Figure 4 presents the best-fit solution of the SEIQRDP model (points) and its projection (lines) until August (2020) in logarithmic scale, using a standard LSE solver [28] for iterative matching of the predicted trajectories to the real data. The dotted line in Figure 4 illustrates the onset of a subsequent surge of the outbreak if all the mitigation measures (quarantine) was to be deactivated immediately (April 15th).

Fig. 4. SEIQRDP best-fit model (points) and its projection (lines) for marginally (1.08:1) under-reported $I(t)$, $D(t)$ and $R(t)$ until August (2020) in logarithmic scale.

Table 2 presents the values for all the SEIQRDP parameters for the best-fit solution. Given the estimated under-reporting of confirmed cases $I(t)$ in Greece during that period, two additional scenarios were tested besides the ‘minimal’ scenario: one for the medium estimation of 4.5:1 and one for the high estimation of 9.5:1. The best-fit solutions for the corresponding SEIQRDP model of all three scenarios presented comparatively. It is worth noting that the only major difference between the three solutions is with the λ parameter, i.e., the rate between ‘quarantine’ and ‘recovered’ compartments (see Figure 3).

Summarizing the SEIQRDP best-fit solutions for the first period of the national epidemic, including various scenarios of infections under-reporting, estimations of peak $I(t)$ dates for Greece are presented in Table 3. Note that, given the epidemic phase uncertainty due to the still limited data series, no ex-

Table 2. LSE-optimal SEIQRDP model parameters in Eq.2 through Eq.8 for Greece (26-Feb-2020 to 14-Apr-2020), minimal ($\rho = 1.08$), medium ($\rho = 4.5$) and high ($\rho = 9.5$) under-reporting of infections.

SEIQRDP parameter	minimal ($\rho = 1.08$)	medium ($\rho = 4.5$)	high ($\rho = 9.5$)
α	0.1030	0.1156	0.1180
β	3.0000	3.0000	3.0000
γ	0.1186	0.1917	0.2435
δ	0.0352	0.0067	0.0013
λ	2.9986	0.5296	3.0000
κ	0.0468	0.0380	0.0241

act value estimations are presented for $I(t)$. Nevertheless, the goodness-of-fit of the SEIQRDP solutions provides a valid ‘explanation’ for the dynamics of the national epidemic during that period, i.e., the interaction between the compartments. Thus, the overall shape and scale of the corresponding curves can be considered as safe for general assessments, including peak $I(t)$ dates.

Table 3. SEIQRDP projections for Greece based on the currently available epidemic data (26-Feb-2020 to 14-Apr-2020), for various scenarios of infection under-reporting.

Under-reporting scenario for $I(t)$	Peak $I(t)$ date
none (1.0:1)	15-Apr
marginal (1.08:1)	16-Apr
‘low’ (4.5:1)	25-Apr
‘high’ (9.5:1)	5-May

Incorporating further data during the months that followed, the SEIQRDP model was updated on a daily basis. Figure 5 presents the best-fit solution of the SEIQRDP model (points) and its projection (lines) until August (2020) in linear scale.

Table 4 presents the values for all the SEIQRDP parameters for the corresponding best-fit LSE solution. The second column contains the values estimated in the first update (April 14th), while the third column contains the values estimated with data up to and including the second update (May 3rd). It should be noted that, due to the fact that much more data were available in the second compared to the first update [11] and a recovered version $\hat{R}(t)$ was used, the current SEIQRDP model fit does not include any inflation factor for $I(t)$ for addressing under-reporting effects. Similarly to the exploration of different under-reporting scenarios for infections, the most notable difference between the two best-fit values is with the ‘cure rate’ λ parameter. The latest value can be considered more reliable than the earlier one, since it is estimated based on more epidemic data and reconstructed $\hat{R}(t)$.

Fig. 5. SEIQRDP best-fit model (points) and its projection (lines) for $I(t)$, $D(t)$ and $R(t)$ until August (2020) in linear scale.

Table 4. LSE-optimal SEIQRDP model parameters in Eq.2 through Eq.8 for Greece (26-Feb-2020 to 3-May-2020), with no inflation factor for $I(t)$ under-reporting and reconstructed $\hat{R}(t)$.

Parameter	Apr 14th	May 3rd
α	0.1030	0.0905
β	3.0000	3.0000
γ	0.1186	0.1114
δ	0.0352	0.0638
λ	2.9986	0.0263
κ	0.0468	0.0679

Based on the additional epidemic data available up to May 3rd and more reliable estimation of $\hat{R}(t)$, the SEIQRDP model fit provided an even better description of the outbreak characteristics in Greece compared to the April 14th update. The model essentially confirms the estimations of the outbreak peak regarding the projected dates around April 19th from very early on, even when only the first 7-10 days of April data were becoming available. The peak was realized on April 20th with $I(t) = 1,860$ according to the actual reported $R(t)$.

Regarding the under-reporting of infections $I(t)$, government officials have stated in formal briefings that it might be up to 20:1 (only 1 in 20 infections registered) or more, at least during the first six months of the national epidemic, a claim that was also supported at the level of at least 6.5:1 to 10:1 by other independent studies. On May 3rd, the scientific committee stated that the true number of infections, including a large number of asymptomatic carriers, is probably around 20,000-30,000, compared to a little over 2,000 which was the officially registered number of confirmed infections at that time.

Using the revisited epidemic data from late April to early May regarding confirmed infections in Greece, and examining the SEIQRDP predictions for peak in Table 3 under the three under-reporting scenarios presented above in Table 2, a rough estimation of the actual under-reporting level can be obtained. Specifically, using a simple linear regression for the dates in Table 3 and the actual peak date for confirmed infections during that period, the corresponding under-reporting factor can be estimated between 2.60 and 2.98, i.e., indicating under-reporting level for $I(t)$ no more than 1:3.

4 Higher-order and spectral modelling

For a more in-depth analysis of the basic data curves $I(t)$, $D(t)$ and $R(t)$ of the COVID-19 epidemic in Greece, the corresponding time series were investigated in terms of linear and periodic trends, i.e., analyse them into their primary frequency components [11].

One of the most important factors, regardless of the long-term approximation of the underlying system, is the analysis of the step-wise dependencies between successive data points, especially the confirmed cases $I(t)$. In statistical terms, this is done by estimating the auto-correlation in the time series for various lags, which produces a quantitative description of dependencies between dates, i.e., separated by a specific number of days. Figure 6 presents the normalized auto-correlation plot of $\Delta I(t)$ (blue), i.e., the daily increases of $I(t)$. Compared to the same plot in the status update on April 14th [11], it is evident here that the two sides of the lobe are almost entirely linear and the LR lines (red) in each side. Additionally, they seem to have become more ‘flattened’ compared to the reference line (green) that corresponds to the case of $\Delta I(t) = c$, i.e., for constant daily increase of $I(t + \tau) = c\tau + I(t)$. There is also a distinct narrow band in the central part, which indicates an even stronger correlation between successive values, i.e., more stable and ‘linearized’ evolution. This proves that, at

least in asymptotic behaviour towards the current state, $I(t)$ increase in Greece was gradually becoming linear during that time period.

Fig. 6. Normalized auto-correlation plots of $\Delta I(t)$ (blue), the LR lines (red) in each side and the reference line (green) of the case of $\Delta I(t) = c$ (constant).

Another way to track the periodic ‘bursts’ of newly reported infections as they are reported on a daily basis is to track the changes in the short-term slope of $\Delta I(t)$. Instead of approximating the entire $I(t)$ curve as in Eq.1 for estimating the long-term behaviour, a short-term temporal window can be used to approximate the LR slope of $I(t)$ as it progresses, i.e., the amplitude and sign of $\Delta I(t)$ changes over few subsequent days. Figure 7 illustrates such a short-term tracking of $\Delta I(t)$ via the 1st-order differential $d \log \hat{b}_1(t)/dt$ of LR slope of $I(t)$, where \hat{b}_1 is the LR slope estimated over a four-day sliding window. In other words, the $\Delta^2 I(t)$ is estimated over a short-term sliding window of almost half a week.

The main curve (magenta) in Figure 7 is the short-term LR slope value for $I(t)$ as it evolves; the arrow annotations indicate decreasing (green) or increasing (red) trends; the asterisks (blue) on the x-axis indicate the major events regarding the activation of mitigation measures in Greece [11]. Finally, the asymptotically fading sinusoid (black) is a LSE-fitted approximation of $g(t)$ by $\hat{g}(t)$, as defined by Eq.9, Eq.10 and Eq.11.

$$g(t) = \frac{d \log \hat{b}_1(t)}{dt} \quad (9)$$

$$\hat{g}(t) = \text{poly3}(z(t)) = \sum_{k=0}^3 p_k z(t)^k \quad (10)$$

Fig. 7. 4-day sliding window slope of $\Delta I(t)$ (magenta), annotations of increasing/decreasing daily trends (red/green) and LSE-fitted approximation.

$$z(t) = \alpha_2 \sin(\alpha_1 t - \alpha_0) + (\beta_1 t + \beta_0) \quad (11)$$

The LSE-optimal parameters of this multi-level approximation are presented in Table 5 with data up to and including May 3rd.

Table 5. LSE-optimal function parameters in Eq.10 and Eq.11 for Greece.

Parameter	optim.value	conf.interval
α_2	0.017	(-0.011, 0.046)
α_1	0.466	(0.382, 0.551)
α_0	-9.502	(-12.980, -6.024)
β_1	-0.005	(-0.017, 0.007)
β_0	0.304	(0.073, 0.535)
p_3	4.142	(-17.500, 25.780)
p_2	3.022	(-4.415, 10.460)
p_1	0.115	(-0.490, 0.720)
p_0	0.010	(-0.019, 0.039)

The approximation curve in Figure 7 clearly indicates three major factors: (a) periodic trend, captured by the first part of Eq.11 with α_i parameters, (b) linear decreasing trend, captured by the second part of Eq.11 with β_j parameters, and (c) asymptotically fading trend, captured by the 3rd-degree polynomial of Eq.10 with p_k parameters. The periodic trend parameters, more specifically the $\alpha_1 = 0.466$, can be translated from radians to daily temporal range via $\alpha_1/2\pi = t/T$ where $T = 68d$ is the length of the data series (May 3rd) since the first confirmed infection case (February 26th), hence yielding a period $t_p = \alpha_1 T/2\pi \approx 0.074166T \approx 5.043d$. This is marginally smaller than the April 14th update (5.56d) and, again, coincides with the empirical data regarding the incubation (asymptomatic) period of COVID-19, estimated at 5.1-5.2 days [16, 15].

5 Human activities and epidemic spread

COVID-19 is the first pandemic humanity has faced after a century with the Spanish flu. It is also the first since the globalisation and urbanisation of human societies. Within few months, the virus expanded from China’s Wuhan region to the entire world, with rigorousness at the highly networked and urbanised North America and Europe. This is why the COVID-19 pandemic is described as a *tertiary domain’s virus* [14].

Just like any other highly contagious flu-like virus, human mobility, social interaction and commuting are crucial factors in the evolution of the outbreak and the success of any targeted mitigation policy. This is the second viewpoint for analysing the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic, i.e., in relation to social activities, as another major driver of the epidemic modelling.

In order to control virus’ expansion, most countries took mitigation measures to limit people’s movements at international, national, or even regional scale. For instance, they enforced strict controls (spatial, temporal, etc.) on urban movement, whereas they prohibited international air and land connections. This was on the basis of controlled mobility, according to the *‘lower and delay epidemic peak’* principle (Figure 8).

Fig. 8. The ‘lower and delay the epidemic peak’ principle. (Source: [5])

During the pandemic the majority of European countries, including Greece, kept restricting what they considered to be unnecessary movements, e.g. moving from a municipality to another or even moving by car for leisure. On the other hand, some other countries, especially eastern Asian countries, chose a different strategy focusing mainly on individual protection measures and personal diagnostic tests without strict mobility prohibitions. This differentiation is clearly

presented in Table 6, where European countries present dramatic reduction of some activities, even at the level of 50%.

Additionally, several technological options were explored for the first time in such an extent, with contact tracing being probably the most celebrated approach [1, 19, 23, 8]. However, it was soon established that such solutions are deteriorated by several problems in practice, mostly due to the fact that the notion of ‘contact’ is very different between wireless technologies (e.g. LTE, Bluetooth, WiFi, RFID, etc) and actual proximity in terms of human-to-human virus transmission. Nevertheless, these options are still explored and combined with other sensing modalities, like the electronic tickets used massively in public transportation within large urban regions.

Table 6. Mobility shift (by activity) in example countries, three from Europe and three from eastern Asia (with and without strict mobility controls, respectively); period: Feb. 13, 2020 – Mar. 27, 2021; baseline refers to Jan. 13, 2020. (Source: Google, 2021 [12])

activity	Greece	Italy	UK	S. Korea	Singapore	Taiwan
retail & recreation	-54%	-49%	-55%	-10%	-6%	-7%
grocery & pharmacy	+14%	-1%	-5%	+12%	+12%	+3%
parks	+45%	-18%	-19%	-13%	-6%	-1%
transit stations	-45%	-47%	-54%	-15%	-12%	+1%
workplaces	-24%	-27%	-21%	-7%	+4%	-1%
residential	+8%	+12%	+11%	+5%	+7%	-1%

In the following, we dig into the details of the temporal resolution of mobility changes, at national versus urban scale. In particular, Figure 9 illustrates the mobility changes in Greece, as a whole, versus Athens, where almost half of the population of the country lives in. Two curves are illustrated in the charts referring to driving (in red) and walking (in brown); this information reflects requests for directions by Apple Maps users [2]. These charts reveal that:

- During the first wave of the pandemic (roughly from Feb. 2020 to May 2020), movement (by any means) degrades drastically. Starting from May, there is a gradual increase of movement, as expected, with a peak during the summer period.
- During the second wave of pandemic (roughly from Oct. 2020 to Mar. 2021), the lowering pattern appears again, although much smoother than the one that appeared in the first wave.

More specifically, in March 2020, strict mobility measures were enforced leading to a reduction of -80% for walking and driving, which lasted until early May 2020. After that, there was the ‘summer high peak’, with the extreme scores of +140% for driving and almost +160% for walking. Autumn 2020 started with an initial slow down, which was followed by a sharp decrease due to the second round of strict mobility measures. Since then and until March 2021, driving and walking remained around -40% with respect to the baseline.

Fig. 9. Mobility variation (by transport means) globally in Greece (left) versus Athens (right); period: Jan. 13, 2020 - Mar. 27, 2021; baseline refers to Jan. 13, 2020. (Source: Apple, 2021 [2])

Nevertheless, walking is a type of mobility that refers to a place where people are familiar with, like for instance their neighbourhood. Hence, there is a limited need for Google or Apple map apps. So, we can safely infer that walking is even more popular (compared with driving and mass transit) than what is illustrated in these figures, if we also take into account the strict distance restrictions that some governments have employed (in Greece, movement for leisure or sports was constrained within the same municipality or a 2 km distance). At urban scale, Athens had a lower peak level than Greece had at national scale.

Interesting findings arise from these data explorations: movement is more restricted in big urban centres (capitals and big cities) compared to smaller towns and countryside; this can be justified by the fact that densely populated areas enforce stricter controls and, in cases where horizontal measures were taken at national scale, they were supervised more strictly than elsewhere. Moreover, there are big differences in lifestyle between big cities and small towns or villages: in a large metropolitan area, mobility prohibition drastically changes the daily routine of people during working or leisure time, whereas in places with lower level of urbanisation, it is much easier to maintain the same routine by favouring e.g. walking or cycling instead of car driving or using public transport.

Last but not least, there is a relationship between the density of population with the number of COVID cases, which shows that this tertiary domain's virus is biased towards the big, industrialised, interconnected urban centres.

6 Correlation of human activity with epidemic spread

In order to produce useful predictive analytics, the human mobility data have to be combined and compared to the epidemic data. For Greece, mobility data from Google and Apple as presented above were available for several regional-scale geographic partitions, but with significantly later than the actual time period reported. Nevertheless, post-analysis was possible in correlation to the corrected

and restored epidemic data for those same regions of Greece, synchronized in time scale.

Three regions of interest were selected for such post-analysis, on the basis of three criteria: (a) density of the native population, (b) being major transit or destination regions during the summer, and (c) availability of both human mobility and epidemic data. Figures 10, 11 and 12 present combined plots of mobility intensity (various types) and confirmed infections on a daily basis, for Attica, Aegean islands (Dodecanese, Lesbos, Samos, Chios) and Crete (Heraklion, Lasithi, Rethymno, Chania), from the beginning of the national outbreak and for a full year afterwards.

Fig. 10. Combined plots of mobility intensity (various types) and confirmed infections on a daily basis for the Attica region (Google data, 3/3/2020-12/2/2021, 5-day moving average).

There are two milestones to be considered in these plots. The first one is the enforcement of the initial, very strict country-wide lockdown during March. As expected, this caused a sharp drop in all types of mobility trends, more evident in Attica region due to the time period (non-tourist) and predominant types of activities (mostly to and from work). The second milestone is the beginning of opening the borders during the summer of 2020, mostly in mid-July. Although there are several periods of missing data in the data series as seen in the plots, it is clear that a second, very intense surge of the epidemic starts building up exactly at that time period and evidently manifested in a much larger scale by end of September and early October.

Given that there is a delay between infections in the general population and the actual reporting after confirmation due to the incubation period of the SARS-CoV-2 virus [11], it is expected that a time shift of at least 1-3 weeks is expected between these two trends. Indeed, such an effect can be seen in the plots for the Crete region during mid-August and, more evidently, in the plots for the Aegean

Fig. 11. Combined plots of mobility intensity (various types) and confirmed infections on a daily basis for the Aegean islands region: Dodecanese, Lesbos, Samos, Chios (Google data, 3/3/2020-12/2/2021, 5-day moving average).

Fig. 12. Combined plots of mobility intensity (various types) and confirmed infections on a daily basis for the Crete region: Heraklion, Lasithi, Rethymno, Chania (Google data, 3/3/2020-8/2/2021, 5-day moving average).

islands region. Regardless of this arbitrary time shift and in order to quantify these correlations in the long term throughout a full year, simple statistical analysis can provide such hints. Figure 13 illustrates in tabular coloured format the three regions, with time period partitioned into three sub-ranges (summer 2020, late 2020, early 2021), with Pearson’s correlation coefficient [26] of confirmed infections against the various types of human mobility, same as in Figures 10, 11 and 12. The time sub-ranges correspond to the three main phases before, during and after the second surge of the national epidemic, in association to the change in behavioural patterns and the opening of the borders during the summer (tourist period).

	CORRELATION with daily confirmed (new)	retail_and_recreation_percent_change_from_baseline	grocery_and_pharmacy_percent_change_from_baseline	parks_percent_change_from_baseline	transit_stations_percent_change_from_baseline	workplaces_percent_change_from_baseline	residential_percent_change_from_baseline
Athens	1/7/20...21/8/20	-0,938	-0,942	-0,570	-0,964	-0,962	0,338
	12/9/20...20/12/20	-0,642	-0,338	-0,673	-0,604	-0,614	0,655
	21/12/20...12/2/21	0,169	-0,139	0,284	0,429	0,376	-0,506
Crete	1/7/20...21/8/20	0,769	0,713	0,790	0,785	-0,352	-0,472
	12/9/20...20/12/20	-0,414	-0,517	-0,560	-0,529	-0,430	0,385
	21/12/20...12/2/21	0,552	-0,169	-0,020	0,200	0,502	-0,748
Aegean	1/7/20...21/8/20	0,733	0,833	0,715	0,744	0,476	-0,438
	12/9/20...20/12/20	-0,622	-0,621	-0,627	-0,635	-0,652	0,652
	21/12/20...12/2/21	0,404	0,256	0,268	0,429	0,244	-0,274

Fig. 13. Pearson’s correlation coefficient [26] of confirmed infections against the various types of human mobility three regions in Greece, with time period partitioned into three sub-ranges (summer 2020, late 2020, early 2021).

Based on the correlation values in Figure 13, it is safe to draw some very important conclusions regarding the effectiveness of the mitigation policies implemented during each time period:

- During the first phase (mid-summer), there is a very strong negative correlation of the reported infections with most types of mobility, especially in the Attica region; this is expected, as Attica is a departure node for summer holidays for both natives and tourists, hence a sharp drop in regional mobility is in contrast to the underlying infections rate.
- During the same period, both Aegean islands and Crete regions show a very clear positive correlation between infections and most mobility types; this is also expected, as these regions host more than half the total non-local population (on holidays), both natives and tourists.
- During the second phase, i.e., after the tourist period, the Attica region continues to show similar but much smaller negative correlation compared to the summer, while the tourist regions shift from positive to negative as non-local populations leave and mobility drops sharply.

- In the third phase when the subsequent surge of the epidemic is escalating throughout the country, correlations shift to positive in all three regions.
- The one type of mobility that seems to illustrate somewhat adverse behaviour from the rest is associated with the ‘residential’ category; this is also expected, since this is associated to limited activities usually close to home, i.e., more or less complementary to the others.

It should be noted that Greece may not be a compatible example of a country in terms of geographical size, population and human flows. It is located at the south-eastern region of the EU, encompassing numerous islands in the eastern Mediterranean Sea, which makes it both a gateway for travellers and a very active destination for summer tourists. On the other hand, it has limited extent with medium/high connectivity within the country. This makes the human flow patterns inherently periodic, high-density near the peaks (July-August) and multi-national in terms of countries of origin. Other paradigms have emerged during the COVID pandemic, especially in Asia, where for example India is significantly different in all these aspects. Therefore, data-driven approaches and proper treatment of all these aspects must be taken into account in a per-country case, in order to produce realistic models with actionable outputs for the decision-makers.

In summary, the lessons learnt from the paradigm of Greece can guide the decision-makers to:

- closely monitor the border crossings and airports with respect to human flows, especially during periodic peaks (e.g. summer);
- employ extensive tracking of infections using pre-emptive screening of inbound travellers to the maximum possible extent;
- constantly model and update the mobility flows and connections within the country, in order to capture the seasonal trends in flow density (not only regarding tourists);
- employ predictive analytics with updated epidemic data, in order to have early warnings for regional possible ‘hot zones’, hence employing pre-emptive mitigation policies, ranging from more strict monitoring to complete but local lockdowns.

7 Conclusions

In this chapter, three main aspects of epidemic modelling were presented in detail, with Greece and its SARS-CoV-2 outbreak during 2020-2021 as a use case. Epidemic monitoring and predictive analytics are usually constrained by strong assumptions regarding the underlying system dynamics, as well as the limited availability of timely and reliable epidemic data. This usually leads to severe degradation of the accuracy and look-ahead capabilities, thus making these tools of limited value to decision-makers in formulating proper emergency response and mitigation policies.

Standard approaches and computational models like the ‘compartmentalized’ SEIR variants are the ‘golden rule’ for establishing a well-established baseline of predicting the short-term evolution and trends of an active outbreak. Moreover, having additional ‘compartments’, e.g. for quarantined population, further enhances the predictive value and the insights about the inherent characteristics of the disease. Human mobility analytics is a recent, very powerful modality of data that enables fine-scale mapping of dynamics and flows, especially in densely populated areas and urban nodes, associating them with commuting and spreading patterns.

Employing powerful algorithms and modern computing resources, the underlying real-world dynamics and highly volatile behaviour of the outbreak evolution can be modelled and analysed with a wide range of approaches from signal processing, adaptive filtering, applied statistics and Machine Learning. Future work should be focused on gathering more specific regional data, extensive monitoring of the human flows at the border crossings and airports, as well as on the inherent characteristics of each country paradigm, especially in geographical extent, population and mobility infrastructure, i.e., aviation, maritime and land connections.

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